

BIOECOLOGY AND DISTRIBUTION OF PLUMS

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Abstract: This article provides information on the bioecology and distribution of the Plum scale (*Chlidaspis prunorum* Borchs), a sucking pest that seriously damages plum trees. High-quality harvest from orchards is one of the urgent problems, and it has been determined that sucking pests cause serious damage.

Key words: Plum, pest, Plum shield (*Chlidaspis prunorum* Borchs). sucking.

Enter. In our republic, integrated protection of plants is carried out on a large scale. Among the sucking pests that harm fruit trees, apple aphids and scale insects cause great damage. These belong to a specific group of insects, they feed on the sap of plants, often the shields cause pathological changes in the tissue of the plant, as a result of which it causes the shedding of leaves and fruits, some it dries out the branches and branches, the quantity of the harvest decreases and the quality deteriorates. In some cases, it can cause the whole plant to dry up. In addition, red or orange spots appear on the bark and fruits of the plant due to the absorption of shields, which reduces the taste and quality of the fruit product, and they do not develop to the normal size. California and Purple Shields usually do this damage.

Most coccids are very omnivorous insects, especially during the hot season and when the relative humidity of the air is low, they absorb more cell sap than the body can digest. This leads to the release of feces containing sugar. Sticky and juicy drops called "honey dew" cover leaves, fruits and branches. Black fungi appear in these juicy wastes and interfere with photosynthesis in the leaves, resulting in negative changes in the appearance and physiology of fruit trees. Among the coccids in orchards, Turon false, Purple, California and Central Asian comma shields are more important. They are found in all parts of Uzbekistan and cause great damage to fruit growing.

Plum shield (*Chlidaspis prunorum* Borchs). The body of the female is pear-shaped or oval, orange in color. The tips of the whiskers are hairless and have two tufts at the end. Pygidium with wide 2-3 pairs of lobes. The first pair is notched on the inner edge, the lobes of the second and third pairs are divided into two, and the crowns are hairy. The shield of the female is covered with hairy yellow or orange caterpillar skins, which protrude from the head of the shield. posterior part of shield broad and moderately swollen, length about 1.6 mm. The nymph shields of males are long, some of them are almost white, oval in shape. The segmental part is covered with hairy filaments, the length of the shield is 1-1.2 mm, the skin of the worm is light yellow.

Plum shields are widespread on fruit trees in the oasis and mountain regions of the Central Asian republics. Apart from Central Asia, it is found in Armenia, Iran, and Afghanistan. It was found in Tashkent, Samarkand, Fergana, Surkhandarya, Bukhara, Khorezm, Andijan regions of Uzbekistan. It is also common in Tajikistan and Turkmenistan. Infests many species of fruit trees, females feed on branches and twigs of apricots, cherries, plums, almonds. It causes significant damage to cherry and plum. The female plum beetle hibernates in the form of an imago on thin branches. It gives birth twice a year.

1-Picture. Plum shields

Biology and distribution of the peach false shield. Young females are orange with dark transverse stripes, adults are reddish-brown, same color, 5-10.5 mm long. The mustache is 8-jointed. The legs are thinner and longer than the mustache. Males

have not been found in Central Asia yet. Males in the Caucasus are larger, up to 8 mm long, light brown. His mustache has 10 joints, his eyes have 3 pairs. The nymph of males has an oblong shield on the front.

Summary. In order to fight against the spread of plum beetles, which are considered the main sucking pests of plums, and to reduce the damage caused, it is necessary to control the level of damage, taking into account each tree damaged in the areas where these pests are spread, and on this basis, organize from early spring to late autumn. - timely and high-quality implementation of agricultural activities, as well as agrotechnical activities against pests, in particular, processing between rows of trees, quality autumn plowing, providing irrigation water, mineral and local fertilizers effective use of dogs, additional feeding of especially damaged trees, removal of weeds and plant debris under trees are also necessary measures.

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